

Substituent Effect on the Strength of Intramolecular Hydrogen Bonding in Schiff's Bases

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A large number of substituted salicylidene-anilines were prepared to study the effect of the substituents on the strength of intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the phenolic proton and the imine nitrogen. A wide range of electron withdrawing and donating groups to vary the basicity of the imine nitrogen and the hydroxyl acidity were substituted in the salicylidene as well as in the aniline ring of the Schiff's bases. It was found by nmr studies that the strength of the hydrogen bonding between the phenolic proton and the imine nitrogen is very much dependent upon the nature of the substituents present in both the rings; substituents which decrease the basicity of the phenolic oxygen increase the strength of hydrogen bonding while those which decrease the basicity of the imine nitrogen decrease the strength of hydrogen bonding and vice-versa. The strength of hydrogen bonding is also enhanced by the electron donating groups at C₇ in place of aldehydic proton.

INTEREST in the general spectroscopy of Schiff's bases has been stimulated^{7,9,10-14} mainly due to the existence of photochromic behaviour⁸⁻⁶ in some of them. Photochromism among Schiff's bases has been attributed to the existence^{1-3,16} of intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the phenolic proton and the imine nitrogen, leading to intramolecular proton transfer followed by *cis-trans* isomerization yielding a photochromic coloured species⁵⁻⁶ on excitation. Visually, the photochromism results in change of the colour of the anil from yellow to orange-red.

A thorough study of the effect of the substituents on the strength of intramolecular hydrogen bonding has been possible with the help of nmr studies of the variously substituted Schiff's bases derived from salicylaldehydes and *o*-hydroxyketones. Photochromism among Schiff's bases has been said to be dependent upon the strength of hydrogen bonding formed between the phenolic proton and the imine nitrogen⁸. Nuclear magnetic resonance studies of the Schiff's bases yield information on the position of the phenolic proton between the phenolic oxygen and the imine nitrogen, and hence the strength of hydrogen bonding. But the interpretation of these studies inevitably involves certain assumptions, i.e., the phenolic proton is more closer to the phenolic oxygen (a case of decreased strength of hydrogen bonding), then it will get shielded and if it lies away from the phenolic oxygen, i.e., closer to imine nitrogen (a case of increased strength of hydrogen bonding) along the -O-H.....N coordinate it will get deshielded.

Dudek and Dudek¹⁴ showed by the nmr studies of variety of Schiff's bases that the phenolic proton resides predominantly on oxygen in N-aryl Schiff's bases while N-alkyl Schiff's bases exist in the *cis*-keto form.

A recent infra-red studies in KBr disc as well in different solvents by Ledbetter¹⁵ has established the

dependency of keto-enol equilibrium among Schiff's bases on the nature of the substituents; the substituents which increase the basicity of the imine nitrogen or the acidity of phenolic proton favours the *cis*-keto-form and vice-versa confirming their own earlier observations^{10,18} of uv and visible spectral studies.

A thorough nmr spectral study of the Schiff's bases in the present work indicates that all these anils exist in strongly intramolecular hydrogen bonded enolic state except those of cyclohexylamine which primarily exists in *cis*-keto form.

Experimental

The following Schiff's bases (Table 1) were prepared by appropriate condensation of aldehydes or *o*-hydroxyketones with corresponding amines by refluxing in ethanol or by heating at 180° without any solvent followed by recrystallisation from pet. ether-acetone.

Purity of these anils has been checked by tlc, and were well characterized by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral data.

Results and Discussion

NMR data of the phenolic protons of the Schiff's bases (I-XXIV) are given in Table 1.

7-Methylsalicylidene-anilines(I-VII): It has been observed that the phenolic protons of all these anils (I-VII) (Fig. 1) are shifted downfield in the nmr spectra by a value of more than 1.2 δ (Table 1) as compared to that of simple salicylidene-aniline, except in case of 7-methylsalicylidene-cyclohexylamine which primarily exists in *cis*-keto form since it shows a broad band centered at 3.64 δ (region of N-H) instead of absorbing around 14 δ (due to phenolic protons). Thus, phenolic protons of all these Schiff's bases (II-VII) have been deshielded as compared to that of simple salicylidene-aniline.

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	Name of the Schiff's base	m.p. ^o	δ Value of the phenolic proton (ppm)
I.	7-Methylsalicylidene-cyclohexylamine	65	N-H : 3.64
II.	7-Methylsalicylidene-aniline	89	14.1
III.	7-Methylsalicylidene- <i>o</i> -toluidine	88-9	14.08
IV.	7-Methylsalicylidene- <i>m</i> -toluidine	90	13.98
V.	7-Methylsalicylidene- <i>p</i> -toluidine	70	14.26
VI.	7-Methylsalicylidene-(<i>p</i> -ethoxy) aniline	78	14.58
VII.	7-Methylsalicylidene-(N, N-dimethyl <i>p</i> -amino) aniline	118	14.75
VIII.	7-Benzylsalicylidene-aniline	126	13.90
IX.	7-Benzylsalicylidene- <i>o</i> -toluidine	115	13.97
X.	7-Benzylsalicylidene- <i>m</i> -toluidine	104	14.00
XI.	7-Benzylsalicylidene- <i>p</i> -toluidine	120	13.95
XII.	7-Phenylsalicylidene-cyclohexyl-amine	110	N-H : 3.24
XIII.	7-Phenylsalicylidene-aniline	140	13.85
XIV.	7-Phenylsalicylidene- <i>o</i> -toluidine	120	13.88
XV.	7-Phenylsalicylidene- <i>m</i> -toluidine	84-85	13.86
XVI.	7-Phenylsalicylidene- <i>p</i> -toluidine	95	13.88
XVII.	7-Phenylsalicylidene- <i>p</i> -ethoxy) aniline	121	13.48
XVIII.	(Salicylidene- <i>o</i> -amino) benzophenone	107	11.26
XIX.	(Salicylidene- <i>m</i> -amino) benzophenone	112	12.60
XX.	(Salicylidene- <i>p</i> -amino) benzophenone	134	12.47
XXI.	(5-Methylsalicylidene- <i>o</i> -amino) benzophenone	109	11.19
XXII.	(5-Methylsalicylidene- <i>m</i> -amino) benzophenone	120	12.33
XXIII.	(5-Methylsalicylidene- <i>p</i> -amino) benzophenone	158	12.22
XXIV.	(5-Bromosalicylidene- <i>o</i> -amino) benzophenone	96	11.5
XXV.	(5-Bromosalicylidene- <i>m</i> -amino) benzophenone	173	11.78
XXVI.	(5-Bromosalicylidene- <i>p</i> -amino) benzophenone	190	12.63
XXVII.	(5-Nitrosalicylidene- <i>o</i> -amino) benzophenone	140	12.60
XXVIII.	(5-Nitrosalicylidene- <i>m</i> -amino) benzophenone	210	13.92
XXIX.	(5-Nitrosalicylidene- <i>p</i> -amino) benzophenone	210	13.78

δ Value of the phenolic proton of salicylidene-aniline is 12.73(12.66)^a nmr spectra have been recorded on Varian A 60 MHz spectrometer and chemical shifts have been expressed in ppm. Tetramethyl silane (TMS) was taken as internal reference and spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ and CCl₄.

Further, the phenolic protons of Schiff's bases having *p*-ethoxy(VI) or *p*-N, N-dimethylamino(VII) substituents in the aniline ring are still more deshielded as compared to other Schiff's bases (II-V), which is due to their strong electron donating abilities. In the case of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (12.05 δ) phenolic proton shifted downfield by a value 4.60 δ as compared to single phenol (7.45 δ).

7-Benzylsalicylidene-anilines (VIII-XI) : Phenolic protons of these 7-benzylsalicylidene-anilines(VIII-XI) (Fig. 1) have been observed to be deshielded as their absorption signal (Table 1) have been shifted downfield by a value of more than 1.2 δ as compared to that of simple salicylidene-aniline.

7-Phenylsalicylidene-anilines (XII-XVII) : Phenolic protons of these 7-phenylsalicylidene-anilines (XII-XVII) (Fig. 1) have been shifted downfield by a value of more than 1.1 δ in the nmr spectra as compared to that of simple salicylidene-aniline (Table 1) except in case of 7-phenylsalicylidene-cyclohexylamine(XII) which primarily exists in *cis*-keto form as it shows a broad band centered at 3.24 δ (N-H) region instead of absorbing around 14 δ due to phenolic protons. Further, the phenolic proton of Schiff's bases having *p*-ethoxy(XVII) group in the aniline ring is still more deshielded as compared to other Schiff's bases (XII-XVII), which is due to its strong electrons donating ability.

(Salicylidene-amino) benzophenones (XVIII-XXIV) : In the nmr spectra of all these Schiff's bases (Fig. 1) it has been observed that phenolic protons of *o*-isomers (XVIII, XXI, XXIV and XXVII) absorb at higher fields as compared to those of *p*-isomers (XX, XXII, XXVI and XXIX) which in turn absorb at higher fields as compared to those of *m*-isomers (XIX, XXI, XXV and XXVIII) respectively (Table 1).

Further, the phenolic protons of (5-bromo- and 5-nitrosalicylidene-amino) benzophenones(XXIV-XXVI and XXVII-XXIV) and (5-methylsalicylidene-amino) benzophenones(XXI-XXIII) absorb at lower and higher fields respectively as compared to those of (salicylidene-amino) benzophenones (XVIII-XX) in their nmr spectra, indicating that the electron donating substituents at C₅ shield the phenolic proton while electron withdrawing substituents deshield the phenolic proton. Similarly in the case of salicylaldehyde which absorbed at 10.95 δ (phenolic proton) shifted to downfield in the case of 5-bromo salicylaldehyde and 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (δ value of phenolic proton 11.63) and higher field in the case of 5-methyl salicylaldehyde. Position of the absorption signal of the phenolic proton of a particular Schiff's base in the nmr spectrum depends upon its position along the -O-H...N coordinate^{1a}.

Fig. 1

Any of the substituents (X, Y, Z) which can affect the basicity of either of the phenolic oxygen or imine nitrogen will affect the strength of hydrogen bond between phenolic proton and the imine nitrogen and hence its position along $-O-H \cdots N$ coordinate. Thus, the variation of electron density around phenolic oxygen or imine nitrogen will affect the electron density around phenolic proton and hence its shielding or deshielding takes place.

Substituent X can affect the basicity of oxygen in two ways depending upon its nature whether it is an electron withdrawing group or an electron donating group; an electron donating group will increase the basicity of the phenolic oxygen and hence will shield the phenolic proton, while an electron withdrawing group will decrease the basicity of phenolic oxygen and hence will deshield the phenolic proton. This explains why the phenolic protons of (5-methylsalicylidene-amino) benzophenones (XXI-XXIII) and (5-bromo and 5-nitrosalicylidene-amino) benzophenones (XXIV-XXIV and XXVII-XXIX) absorb at higher and lower fields respectively as compared to those of (salicylidene-amino) benzophenones (XVIII-XX).

If the substituent Z is an electron donor as is in the present case ($-CH_3$, $-CH_2$ -Ph and -Ph), it will increase the basicity of the imine nitrogen and hence increase the strength of the hydrogen bonding between the phenolic proton and imine nitrogen as compared to that of simple salicylidene-aniline; azomethine linkage ($>C=N-$) acts as an electron acceptor at carbon end when linked to a phenyl group and as an electron donor at nitrogen end when linked to a phenyl group⁷. This increased strength of hydrogen bonding will displace the phenolic proton closer to imine nitrogen and hence causing its deshielding.

Thus, deshielding of the phenolic protons of 7-methylsalicylidene-anilines, 7-benzylsalicylidene-anilines and 7-phenylsalicylidene-anilines as compared to that of simple salicylidene-aniline (Table 1) is due to the increased electron density over nitrogen which displaces the phenolic proton away from phenolic oxygen.

Similarly the substituent Y can also shield or deshield the phenolic proton by decreasing or increasing the basicity of the imine nitrogen depending upon its nature i.e., phenolic protons of 7-methylsalicylidene-(*p*-ethoxy) aniline (VI), 7-methylsalicylidene-(*N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-amino) aniline (VII)

and 7-phenylsalicylidene-(*p*-ethoxy) aniline (XVII) are considerably deshielded as compared to those of simple 7-methylsalicylidene-aniline (II) or 7-phenylsalicylidene-aniline (XIII) respectively. Phenolic protons of (salicylidene-amino) benzophenones (XVIII-XX) absorb at higher field as compared to that of simple salicylidene-aniline (Table 1), which is due to the electron withdrawing nature of the benzoyl group. This benzoyl group decreases the basicity of the imine nitrogen to a more extent when at *ortho*, than when at *para*- and the least when at *meta*-position in the aniline ring, and is evident from the absorption signals of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-isomers at 11.26 δ , 12.60 δ and 12.47 δ respectively. Similar results have been observed in the case of other (5-methyl, 5-bromo- and 5-nitrosalicylidene-amino) benzophenones (Table 1).

Thus, the position of the phenolic proton between the phenolic oxygen and the imine nitrogen or the strength of the hydrogen bonding in Schiff's bases is dependent upon the substituent present in both the rings as well as at C_7 . In the aniline ring the effect is more when the substituent is at *o*-position than at *para*-position and the least when at *m*-position.

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References

1. G. M. J. SCHMIDT, *Acta Cryst.*, 1957, **10**, 798.
2. M. D. COHEN, Y. HIRSHBERG and G. M. J. SCHMIDT, "Hydrogen bonding", D. HADZI, Ed., Pergamon Press, London, 1959, p. 293.
3. M. D. COHEN and G. M. J. SCHMIDT, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 2442.
4. M. D. COHEN and G. M. J. SCHMIDT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2041.
5. (a) R. S. BECKER and W. F. RICHEY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1298.
(b) R. S. BECKER and W. F. RICHEY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **49**, 2092.
6. (a) R. PETASHNIK and M. OTTOLENGHI, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1969, **51**, 3671.
(b) M. OTTOLENGHI and D. S. McCOLLURE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1967, **46**, 4613, 4620.
7. EL. AASSER and F. ABDEL-HALIM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 590.
8. M. D. COHEN, G. M. J. SCHMIDT and S. FLAVIAN, *J. Chem. Soc. B.*, 1967, 317 (Eng.).
9. F. HASELBACH and E. HEILBRONNER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1968, **51**, 16.
10. W. LEDBETTER JOHN, JR., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2245.
11. E. FISCHER and Y. FREI, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, **27**, 803.
12. J. D. MARGERUM and J. A. SOUSA, *App. Spectrosc.*, 1965, **19**, 91.
13. J. W. LEDBETTER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 2351.
14. G. O. DUDEK and E. P. DUDEK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 2407.
15. J. W. LEDBETTER, JR., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, **81**, 54.
16. S. B. HENDRICKS, O. R. WULF, G. B. HILBERT and U. LIDELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1955.
17. JOHN R. DYER, "Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds"—Prentice-Hall Inc, Englewood Cliffs, N. J.